

A METHOD FOR DETERMINING THE NON-LINEAR TIME DEPENDENCE OF WINDOWED DATA GATHERED FROM SCATTERED SIGNALS

John E. Gray, Theodore R. Rice, Jeffrey E. Conte, Gregory Watson
Code-G71
Naval Surface Warfare Center
Dahlgren, Virginia, 22448
(703-663-1110)

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a discussion of moments associated with functions that are the Fourier transform or Fourier series of time domain signals. The reason for considering moments results from a need to understand what happens to the frequency spread of a transmitted signal after it has been reflected from an object undergoing non-uniform motion. The important example of a sinusoidal wave reflected from an object undergoing constant acceleration is considered. It appears that analytic expressions for moments of finite time signals that are given by well-behaved sums are also applicable to this waveform.

1. INTRODUCTION

A feature common to both radar and sonar is the broadcasting of a time domain signal $s(t)$ that has a simple structure. The signal is scattered from a "target" and the return signal is analyzed for position and velocity information. This information from time domain signals is transformed to the frequency domain to facilitate ease of analysis [1]. This is done by windowing the data over an interval of time, $[-T/2, T/2]$. It is assumed that, if the window is made small enough, the signal has a linear time dependence. In adaptive systems, this is a realistic assumption, but for systems that have preset windows, the signal can have a non-linear functional dependence on the time. This leads to a design mismatch that cannot be completely rectified. It is desirable to find analysis techniques that can determine whether this non-linearity is occurring and convert it to useful information about the scatterer. A technique is discussed that uses the higher order moments in the frequency domain to detect and quantify complex time dependence.

2. MOMENTS OF FUNCTIONS DEFINED OVER ALL \mathbb{R}

For a non-linear scattered signal, the moments of the signal can be used to determine additional information about the signal. The n^{th} centroid moment of a variable x is given by [2]

$$M_n(f) = \frac{\langle x^n \rangle_f}{\langle 1 \rangle_f} = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^n f(x) dx}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) dx}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $M_n(f)$ is the n^{th} moment of x weighted by the function $f(x)$. In the frequency domain, the interest is in computing the frequency spreads or moments from a known frequency spectrum:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \omega^n \rangle_F &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \omega^n F(\omega) d\omega, \\ \langle 1 \rangle_F &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(\omega) d\omega, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

where $F(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of $f(\cdot)$. For certain functions defined over the complete time spectrum, it can be shown that

$$M_n(F) = \frac{(-j)^n f^{(n)}(0)}{f(0)}, \quad (2.3)$$

where (n) indicates the n^{th} derivative of the function. The functions must be members of a class of functions whose derivatives through the n^{th} order, $f^{(1)}(t)$, $f^{(2)}(t)$, \dots , $f^{(n)}(t)$, exist almost everywhere, go to zero as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$, and the integral of $|f^{(m)}(t)|$ from $-\infty < t < \infty$ is finite ($0 \leq m \leq n$).

3. MOMENTS OF FUNCTIONS DEFINED ON THE INTERVAL $[-T/2, T/2]$

For functional representations of physical phenomena, the function $f(t)$ does not necessarily satisfy the conditions listed earlier, particularly for functions considered in this paper, which are windowed over the interval $t \in [-T/2, T/2]$. The Fourier transform, instead of being over an infinite interval, is over the windowed region. For this problem, it is assumed that the signal is periodic in time (i.e., $f(t+NT) = f(t)$ for all integer values of N). Thus, $f(t)$ is expanded in a Fourier series and can be written as

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n e^{\frac{2\pi j n t}{T}}, \quad (3.1)$$

where a_n is given by

$$a_n = \frac{1}{T} \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} f(t) e^{-\frac{2\pi j n t}{T}} dt. \quad (3.2)$$

By choice, the formula for the moments in the frequency domain, with windowing, is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} (-j)^n f^{(n)}(0) &= \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2\pi m}{T} \right)^n a_m \\ &\doteq M_n(F) \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} a_m \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

$$= M_n(F) f(0) = \langle \omega^n \rangle_F,$$

$$M_n(F) \doteq \frac{(-j)^n f^{(n)}(0)}{f(0)},$$

where it is assumed that $f(0) \neq 0$, $\omega_m = 2\pi m/T$, and

$$\sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \left| \left(\frac{2\pi m}{T} \right)^n a_m \right| < \infty, \quad (3.4)$$

The need for the choice made above arises in the following manner. Because one obtains a set of Fourier coefficients when expanding $f(t)$ over any interval $-T-\epsilon \leq t \leq T-\epsilon$ ($-T < \epsilon < T$), there are an infinite number of sets $\{a_n\}$, $-\infty < n < \infty$, for which

$$f(0) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n \quad (3.5)$$

is true. In order to remove the ambiguity, it is

necessary to pick a fixed ϵ in order to make a meaningful comparison between the moments of different functions.

This derivation is simple; one just takes the time derivative of both sides of equation (3.1) n times, sets $t = 0$ on both sides, pulls $M_n(F)$ out of the summation on the right hand side, and then solves for $M_n(F)$ in terms of $f(0)$, $(-j)^n$, and $f^{(n)}(0)$.

4. EXAMPLE OF THE MOMENTS OF A FUNCTION DEFINED ON \mathbb{R}

It can be shown that a signal $f(t)$ that results from the arbitrary signal $g(t)$ being reflected from an object undergoing an arbitrary motion $r(t)$ can be written as [3]

$$f(\tau) = -a(\tau) g(2h(\tau) - \tau), \quad (4.1)$$

where

$$a(\tau) = 2 \frac{dh(\tau)}{d\tau} - 1, \quad (4.2)$$

$h(\tau) = t$, and

$$h(\tau) + \frac{r(h(\tau))}{c} = \tau. \quad (4.3)$$

Here, c is the speed of light, $c = 3 \times 10^8$ m/s. As an example, assume that $r(\cdot)$ is a constant velocity model given by

$$r(\cdot) = r_0 + v_0(\cdot). \quad (4.4)$$

For this example, one obtains

$$h(\tau) = \frac{1}{\beta^+} \left(\tau - \frac{r_0}{c} \right). \quad (4.5)$$

Also, assume that $g(\cdot)$ is given by

$$g(\cdot) = e^{-b \left(\cdot - \frac{2r_0}{\beta^+ c} \right)^2} e^{j d \left(\cdot - \frac{2r_0}{\beta^+ c} \right)}, \quad (4.6)$$

where

$$\beta^+ = 1 + \frac{v_0}{c}, \quad \beta^- = 1 - \frac{v_0}{c}. \quad (4.7)$$

For this modulated Gaussian waveform, one obtains

$$f(\tau) = -\frac{\beta^-}{\beta^+} e^{-\left[\frac{b(\beta^-)^2}{(\beta^+)^2} \right] \tau^2} e^{j d \tau}, \quad (4.8)$$

and

$$F(\omega) = -\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{b}} e^{-\left[\frac{(\beta^+)^2}{4b(\beta^-)^2}\right](\omega-d)^2} \quad (4.9)$$

The first moment (or mean) and second moment of ω for this $F(\omega)$ (computed using Eq. (2.3)) are:

$$\begin{aligned} M_1(F) &= d, \\ M_2(F) &= \frac{2b(\beta^-)^2}{(\beta^+)^2} + d^2, \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

which yields a variance of

$$M_2(F) - [M_1(F)]^2 = \frac{2b(\beta^-)^2}{(\beta^+)^2} \quad (4.11)$$

The results in Eqs. (4.10) and (4.11) are exactly what one would obtain for the mean and variance of the Gaussian distribution given in Eq. (4.8). As seen in Figs. 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3, the width of the peak in the frequency domain decreases with the radial velocity of the receding target. For all of these figures, $b=5$ and $d=1 \times 10^3/s$ while for Fig. 4.1 $v_0 = 1 \times 10^3 m/s$ and for Fig. 4.2 $v_0 = 1.5 \times 10^8 m/s$ (0.5c).

5. MOMENTS OF FUNCTIONS SAMPLED IN THE REGION [0,T]

In practice, a sampled time series is used instead of working with an analog signal. As a result, Eqs. (3.1) and (3.2) become

$$f(kT_0) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} F\left(\frac{2\pi n}{NT_0}\right) e^{\frac{2\pi jnk}{N}} \quad (5.1)$$

and

$$F\left(\frac{2\pi n}{NT_0}\right) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} f(kT_0) e^{-\frac{2\pi jnk}{N}} \quad (5.2)$$

This is just a discrete transform pair over N points with the time signal being sampled every T_0 seconds ($T=NT_0$). However, as a rule, one cannot find moments from this discrete data for the following reason. Assume $f(t)$ has a Fourier series representation given by Eq. (3.1) but on the interval $[0,T]$. Then the m^{th} term of the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is given as

$$F\left(\frac{2\pi m}{N_0 T_0}\right) = N_0 \sum_{\gamma=-\infty}^{\infty} a_{m+\gamma N_0} \quad (5.3)$$

Because the m^{th} term of the DFT is a combination of frequency coefficients from the Fourier series

Figure 4.1. Graph of $f(\tau)$ from Eq. (4.8) for $v_0 = 1 \times 10^3 m/s$.

Figure 4.2. Graph of $f(\tau)$ from Eq. (4.8) for $v_0 = 1.5 \times 10^8 m/s$ (0.5c).

Figure 4.3. Graphs of Equation (17) for $v_0 = 1 \times 10^3 m/s$ (graph 1) and $v_0 = 0.5c$ (graph 2).

(this is called aliasing or frequency foldover), using a term such as

$$\left(\frac{2\pi m}{N_0 T_0}\right) F\left(\frac{2\pi m}{N_0 T_0}\right) \quad (5.4)$$

to generate a moment from the finite DFT coefficients is not realistic.

6. MOMENTS FOR A SAMPLED FUNCTION IN THE REGION [0,T]

There are two possibilities considered when determining moments for the Fourier coefficients, $\{a_n\}$, of sampled functions; when the infinite sums defining the moments for the set $\{a_n\}$ exist when they do not. It is possible to use Eq. (3.3) to evaluate the moments for the set $\{a_n\}$ whose moment sums exist. Apparently, this equation can also be used in certain cases to approximate local moments of the set $\{a_n\}$ when the moments sums for all n do not exist.

A case where the set $\{a_n\}$ does not have converging sums occurs when the wave emitted is a sinusoid. For these waveforms, the signal, $f(t)$, scattered from a boundary undergoing a law of motion $r(t)$ is given as

$$f(\tau) = -\left(2\frac{dh(\tau)}{d\tau} - 1\right) X e^{j\omega_0(2h(\tau) - \tau)} \quad (6.2)$$

where ω_0 is the broadcast frequency. If the object undergoes constant acceleration, then $h(r)$ is given by

$$h(\tau) = \frac{c\beta^+}{a_0} X \left[-1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{2a_0}{(\beta^+)^2 c} \left(\frac{r_0}{c} - \tau\right)} \right] \quad (6.3)$$

where v_0 is the initial velocity and a_0 is the acceleration. As an example, consider an object undergoing a constant acceleration of $a_0 = 1$ to 9 g's ($g = 10\text{m/s}^2$) with $v_0 = 300$ m/s. The received signals, as computed using Eq. (6.2), are shown in Fig. 6.1. These signals only display the Doppler of the reflected signal. Fig. 6.2 shows values of the standard deviation of the peak for various values of a_0 and frequencies from 1 to 100 GHz.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, formulas for the moments of the Fourier transform or the Fourier series of a function have been reviewed and conditions under which they exist have been discussed. Under certain

conditions, it is possible to approximate the local moments of Fourier coefficients associated with time-limited signals that do not possess moment sums. One such signal is the plane wave as illustrated by comparison of the measured standard deviation to that computed using Eq. (3.3). Rigorous analysis of this phenomenon is needed to determine when this approximation can be applied.

Figure 6.1. The Doppler signal from a 10GHz plane wave. Target a_0 ranges from 1 to 9 g's.

Figure 6.2. Computed standard deviation of the signal. Values of a_0 from 1 to 25 g's and frequency from 1 to 100 GHz.

8. REFERENCES

1. Papoulis, Athanasios, *Signal Analysis*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1977, pp 216.
2. Bracewell, Ronald N., *The Fourier Integral and Its Application*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1978, Chapter 8.
3. Gray, J. E., "The Doppler Spectrum of Accelerating Objects", International Radar Conference, Radar-90, May 1990.